

**A new species of the genus *Neoplagionotus* Kasatkin, 2005 from Syria
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Clytini)**

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Abstract: A new species *Neoplagionotus karmelicola* **sp. n.** close to: *N. scalaris* (Brullé, 1832), *N. bobelayei* (Brullé, 1832) and *N. bednariki* Lazarev, 2022 is described from Syria. Dorsal views of holotype and paratype are provided.

Introduction

According to the last Palaearctic Cerambycidae Catalogue (Danilevsky, 2020), the genus *Neoplagionotus* Kasatkin, 2005 included 3 species: *N. scalaris* (Brullé, 1832), *N. bobelayei* (Brullé, 1832) and *N. andreui* (Fuente, 1908). Recently a fourth one was described - *N. bednariki* Lazarev, 2022.

Now new species from Syria is proposed.

Materials and methods

Both photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia).

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University.

Taxonomy

Neoplagionotus karmelicola sp. n.

Figs 1-2

Type locality. Israel, Karmel Mt., Haifa environs.

Description. Two males only are known: holotype, body length: 16.0 mm, body width: 6.0 mm; paratype (in bad condition), body length: 12.9 mm, body width: 5.0 mm.

Integument totally black with numerous areas covered by short recumbent yellow pubescence.

Head transverse, widest at eye level, with dense recumbent yellow pubescence between eyes; frons strongly transverse about as wide, as long, with dense yellow pubescence; occiput and genae also with dense yellow pubescence; eyes very big, about as wide as interantennal space, nearly touching mandibulae bases, strongly emarginated, so genae very narrow; maxillary and labial palpi reddish with elongated apical joints.

Antennae red, surpassing second transverse elytral band, slightly serrate from 6th to 10th joints; scapus wide, about as wide as 7th joint and about 2.0 times longer than wide; 1st joint a little longer than 3rd and much longer than 4th; pedicellum about as long as wide.

Prothorax subglobulose, 1.2 times wider at middle than long, more tapering anteriorly; pronotum regularly convex, with very small, dense punctation; two wide transverse yellow setae bands present; anterior band narrowed at middle, second band moved backwards and evenly curved; prosternum with sparse pubescence.

Elytra about 2.2 times longer than basal width; strongly converging posteriorly, rounded apically; 5 wide transverse elytral bands are well developed; basal band is represented by 2 big oval round spots with yellow scutellum in between; posthumeral band also wide, strongly angulated and protruding anteriorly along suture; lateral humeral spot hardly reaching 2nd elytral band; middle band rather wide, distinctly extends backwards at middle; preapical bands are represented by 2 big round spots; apical band oval, totally covering elytral apices; epipleurae with yellow pubescence to about elytral middle.

Legs reddish, without erect setae, femora slightly widened, not clavate.

Thoracic metasternum with scattered pubescence anteriorly,

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becoming denser posteriorly; metepisternum with dense yellow pubescence.

All visible abdominal sternites densely pubescent with narrow glabrous anterior bands; last abdominal sternites and tergites rounded.

Type material. Holotype (Fig. 1), male with three labels: 1) “Syria / Haifa / Reitter”; 2) [red] “Holotype / *Neoplacionotus* / *KARMELICOLA* sp. n. / M. Lazarev det. 2022”, 3) [pink] ”Зоомузей МГУ (Москва, Россия) / № ZMMU Col 03233 / Zool. Mus. Mosq. Univ. / (Mosquae, ROSSIA) / ex coll. N. N. Plavilstshikov” - ZMM; Paratype (Fig. 2), male with two labels: 1) “Сирия / Латакия / 10/V 1964”, 2) “Paratype / *Neoplacionotus* / *KARMELICOLA* sp. n. / M. Lazarev det. 2022” - MD.

Distribution. The new species is known from Israel and Syria.

Differential diagnosis. The new taxon is externally very similar to *N. scalaris* and *N. bednariki*, but in *N. scalaris* basal elytral band is usually widely interrupted by scutellum and consists of a pair of round spots; third (central) elytral band is about straight (protruding backwards along suture in the new species); fourth elytral band is in form of transverse bar not interrupted at suture (or hardly interrupted), while in *N. karmelicola* **sp. n.** it is in form of a pair of round spots; abdominal sternites in *N. scalaris* and in *N. bednariki*, widely glabrous anteriorly; frons and vertex in *N. scalaris* and in *N. bednariki* are nearly glabrous; legs with rather dark femora.

Etymology. The new species is named after its type locality - Mt. Karmel, where Haifa-city is situated.

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Figs 1-2. *Neoplacionotus karmelicola* sp. n.: 1 - Holotype, male; 2 - Paratype, male.

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